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Research Article

RECOGNIZING LOW AND HIGH SERUM-ASCITES
ALBUMIN GRADIENT IN ASCITIC FLUID BY THE POINT
OF CARE DIPSTICK TEST¹Dr Fariha Imtiaz, ²Dr Unaiza Imtiaz, ³Dr Ehsan Ali¹Avicenna Medical College²Fatima Memorial Medical College³Weifang Medical College

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Abstract:

Aim: To evaluate the capability of ascitic fluid dipstick results for pH, glucose, and protein in order to predict a low serum-ascites albumin gradient (SAAG) at the bedside of the patient in the emergency department (ED).

Methods: This prospective cross-sectional study was conducted for a year duration from January 2019 to January 2020 in the emergency department of the Mayo Hospital Lahore. All patients with diagnostic or therapeutic paracentesis of ascitic fluid were considered as eligible patients. Exclusion criteria included clinical suspicion of spontaneous bacterial peritonitis (PAS), any contraindication to paracentesis and patients refusing to participate in the study. Dipstick values were obtained at the patient's bedside. A low SAAG ascitic fluid was defined as the study outcome. We also used our study population as a test group to evaluate an equation proposed in one previous study: $K = 0.012 \text{ Protein} - 0.012 \text{ Glucose} - 3.329 \text{ pH} + 23.498$

Results: A total of 50 patients were enrolled in the study. Based on multivariate regression analysis, dipstick values for protein and glucose were independently predictive of a low SAAG ascitic fluid ($P = 0.23$, $OR = 1.04$; and $P = 0.001$, $OR = 0.81$, respectively). The formula proposed in one of the previous studies was tested by our data set, with sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), and negative predictive value (NPV) at 84%, 83%, 84%, and 80%, respectively.

Conclusion: Dipstick test for ascitic fluid pH, glucose and protein has acceptable sensitivity and specificity as a supportive point test, but cannot be recommended as an alternative to SAAG based on available results.

Keywords: ascitic serum albumin gradient, ascitic fluid, rod test.

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INTRODUCTION:

Ascitic fluid is often sent to the laboratory for analysis in health centers. Although in many cases the cause Sending ascites fluid to the laboratory for analysis is often done in healthcare facilities. Although the cause of ascites may appear clinically obvious in many cases, but the exact diagnosis must be clarified by analyzing this fluid. The recommended first-line laboratory test for ascitic fluid is ascites albumin gradient (SAAG), followed by other tests based on the results. In the past, ascites fluid with low SAAG was called "exudative ascites" and high SAAG was called "exudative ascites", but these terminology was questioned later and most authors preferred to use "low SAAG" and "high SAAG" instead of "Exudate" and "exudate". Based on the SAAG ascites fluid, a differential diagnosis spectrum can be considered for further analysis. In the case of low SAAG, differential diagnoses may include ascites caused by tuberculosis peritonitis, ascites caused by malignant tumors (e.g. peritoneal cancer, metastases of gastric and ovarian cancer), pancreatic ascites, renal ascites, biliary ascites, bacterial peritonitis, and ascites. On the other hand, high-grade ascites are complicated ascites caused by cirrhosis, ascites caused by heart failure, those caused by extensive liver metastases, and other circumstances such as fulminant liver failure. The ascites fluid spot test using the bayonet was widely studied by some researchers, but the focus was mainly on detecting infections (namely spontaneous bacterial peritonitis [SBP]), not on distinguishing between high and low SAAG values. Some studies have shown the acceptable accuracy of rod tests (leukocyte esterase) to detect peritonitis in ascites fluid, while other studies (including the largest) have shown that the rod test is not sensitive enough to detect SBP. Earlier studies focused on ascitic fluid rod tests, perhaps because timely diagnosis of SBP would be useful in initiating the appropriate empirical antibiotic awaiting culture results. The distinction between low SAAG and ascites fluid with high SAAG using the emergency department (ED) point test may not have this effect, but it can undoubtedly skip the first stage of SAAG determination, which is recommended today if it proves to be reliable enough. In this study, we evaluated the relationship between pH, protein and glucose values with low SAAG (exudative) fluid levels and their predictive value for this result. To distinguish between low SAAG and high SAAG fluids based on our data set.

METHODS:

This prospective cross-sectional study was conducted for a year duration from January 2019 to January 2020 in the emergency department of the Mayo Hospital Lahore. All patients with ascites

admitted to ED were selected. Internal Medicine ED has an annual inventory of approximately 30,000 patient meetings. All patients admitted to EDW, in which the management team performed abdominal diagnostics (e.g. for new ascites) or therapeutic (e.g. ascites with respiratory failure) were considered eligible patients. Exclusion criteria were defined as clinical suspicion of SBP (e.g. fever or abdominal tenderness), any contraindication to paracentesis (e.g. severe coagulopathy) and refusal of patients to participate in the study. All patients read (or had companions read) and signed the informed consent form. Abdominal paracentesis is performed by residents of emergency medicine (post-graduate year (PGY) 1 or 2). Emergency medicine doctor makes a decision about paracentesis. When the ascites fluid volume is estimated to be low, paracentesis is performed after the best place for surgery has been marked by a radiology resident. Paracentesis is performed mainly from the left or right lower quadrant than from the midline in our center. After the patient was included in the study, paracentesis was performed by one of the members of the management team in the presence of our researcher; the researcher was a resident of emergency medicine (PGY 3) responsible for performing the dipstick test and recording all available variables in a previously designed standardized worksheet. The researcher took a 5-10 ml sample to perform bayonet tests according to the manufacturer's instructions, and 10 ml samples in other appropriate tubes were immediately sent to the laboratory for cell counting and cytology, biochemistry (albumin and total protein) and culture. Albumin blood sample was taken simultaneously for each patient to measure serum albumin level. The agreement between the observers was calculated to be 90% (excellent agreement) and the remaining cases of disagreement were resolved by consensus with a third party. The dipstick strips used in this study were urinary sticks with 30, 100 and 500 mg / dL protein cut points; 50, 100, 250 and 500 mg / dl for glucose and 5, 6, 6.5, 7, 8 and 9 for pH. For each patient, SAAG was calculated by subtracting the ascitic albumin from the blood albumin level; both were measured in the hospital laboratory using an auto analyzer (Selectra 2). SAAG was defined as our gold standard and was defined as the definition of high SAAG (> 1.1 mg / dl or earlier exudate) and low SAAG (<1.1 mg / l or earlier exudate). We chose the low level of ascites fluid SAAG as the test result. Scoop values for blood, pH, glucose and protein were read and recorded. For protein and glucose, cut-off points corresponding to the color of the bayonet were recorded as mg / dl. For one-way analysis, continuous data was analyzed by t-test if the data were normally distributed (according to the Kolmogorov-Smirnov, Shapiro and Levene test); otherwise, a customized t-test was used. The

categorical data were compared using the Pearson χ^2 test. A P value below 0.05 was considered statistically significant. In the multivariate model, we have introduced all variables that can predict the result according to our clinical experience. Multivariate analysis was performed by constructing a logistic regression model according to Wald's frontal method. Independent associations have been reported according to the model.

RESULTS:

A total of 50 patients were included in the study. Twenty-nine (58%) are men and 21 (42%) are women. The mean age (SD) was 53.6 (1.8), at least 18 and at most 90. Twenty-nine patients (58%) had high SAAG and 21 patients (42%) had low SAAG levels.

Table 1 shows the properties of ascitic fluids in each group. Test strip values for glucose, protein and pH

were significantly different between the two groups (P <0.001, P = 0.002 and P <0.001, respectively). The mean value measured for laboratory pH was also significantly lower in the low SAAG group, while the values measured for glucose and protein in the laboratory did not differ significantly between the two groups. Test strip values for PH, protein and glucose were introduced into the multivariate regression model. Because glucose and protein values are 3-digit variables, they are divided into 10 to increase their true relationship with the SAAG group. Test strip protein was present and glucose levels in the test strip remained in the final step (P = 0.23, OR = 1.04 and P = 0.001, OR = 0.81, respectively). The test strip pH was not associated with the result in this analysis (P = 0.36). Compared with 100 mg / dL (2+) levels, the 50 mg / dL (1+) test strip was 95% more likely to obtain low SAAG fluid at glucose level. Other relationships can be calculated according to this analysis.

Table 1. Mean (SD) values for glucose, protein, and pH in low SAAG and high SAAG groups

	Laboratory			Dipstick		
	Glucose (mg/dL)	Protein (g/L)	pH	Glucose (mg/dL)	Protein (mg/dL)	pH
Low SAAG	99.8 (74.3)	3.09 (0.8)	7.41 (0.15)	92.3 (52.3)	404.0 (178.3)	7.02 (0.72)
High SAAG	134.5 (66.7)	2.34 (1.7)	7.14 (0.16)	185.4 (68.3)	211.7 (217.1)	7.83 (0.56)
P value	0.09	0.08	<0.0001	<0.0001	0.002	<0.001

We obtained 84% sensitivity, 83% specificity, 84% positive predictive value (PPV) and 80% negative predictive value (NPV) for this equation to predict ascitic fluid under SAAG (previously exudative).

DISCUSSION:

Identifying low or high SAAG ascitic levels in a patient's bed can lead to further emergency ward testing, avoiding a second fluid stroke and shortening admission times. Heidari et al. Assessment of the accuracy of the level indicator bar test to distinguish between high and low SAAGs. Given the work he did, this study is in a different environment and population using the same method. Assessment of the consistency of results. A study by Heidari et al. Found an independent relationship between test strip values (pH, protein and glucose) for ascitic liquid and low SAAG levels (they used the term "exudative" which we preferred not to use). They proposed an equation based on logistic regression analysis and tested sensitivity, specificity, PPV and NPV for a subset of the non-analyzed populations (93.8%, 94.4%, 89.5% and 96.9%, respectively). These high values prompted us to evaluate this formula using a different set of data.

In our study, we found independent relationships between the ascitic indicator of the level of liquid protein and the low-ascitic SAAG ascitic and

glucose values. Although PH was associated with low SAAG fluid levels in one-way analysis, it did not show an independent relationship. This suggests that our data is based on Heidari et al. This meant that it would not produce as much sensitivity, specificity, PPV and NPV as those detected. After entering the values into the formula, we obtained these values as described in the results section. Although these parameters are not as high as those from the previous study, they are still within the acceptable range for the diagnostic point of maintenance test. However, it is strongly recommended that you perform a gold standard test (SAAG detection by the laboratory) with our findings. Some confirmatory tests (ranked after establishing SAAG based on current recommendations) for final diagnosis may be cost effective based on the results of this maintenance point test, but this requires further testing. Profitability.

CONCLUSION:

Dipstick test of ascitic fluid for pH, glucose, and protein has an acceptable sensitivity and specificity as a point of care test. Further studies with larger

populations are needed to recommend for or against its usage as a guide to order further confirmative tests (to identify the cause of cirrhosis) in the ED and decrease the admission time of the patient.

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